

Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper in Alloys Using Acetoacetanilide

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From 150 to 900 μg of copper (II) have been extracted aqueous solutions maintained at pH 7.1 to 8.0 into 10 ml of chloroform in one step using acetoacetanilide as complexing agent and have been determined spectrophotometrically in these extracts at 340 $m\mu$, using reagent blank or pure chloroform as reference. In addition to the advantage of one step extraction, the possibility of the estimation of the metal ion in the presence of appreciable amounts of Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} and F^{-} has been found to be very convenient. Thus copper has been determined in alloys like brass, white metal etc., without the separation of the former ions with high degree of accuracy.

Copper (II) gives colour reactions with a variety of organic compounds and the organic reagents used in the colorimetric detection and determination of this ion are numerous. The most commonly used reagents are amines¹⁻⁵, hydroxylamines^{6,7} or substances containing nitrogen atoms in straight chains or aromatic rings⁸⁻¹⁰. But only a few reagents containing β -diketo grouping, like acetylacetone¹¹ and thenoyl trifluoroacetone¹² have been used for the spectrophotometric estimation of copper (II). Acetoacetanilide, a reagent of this group has been used for the gravimetric determination of copper¹³ in alloys due to its selectivity in presence of other metals commonly present in such alloys. As the green copper-acetoacetanilide complex can be extracted easily in chloroform, the measurement of the absorbance at 340 $m\mu$ against pure solvent has been utilised in a rapid and easy method for the spectrophotometric determination of copper in alloys like brass, bronze and white metal. There is no necessity of prior separation of the other metal ions commonly present in these alloys and the relative standard deviation is only $\pm 1.03\%$

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

Reagents and chemicals :

Copper (II) solution : Pure copper sulphate (E. Merck) was dissolved in water, a few drops of sulphuric acid was added, and the metal content was determined iodometrically. The solution was diluted so that the metal content of the final solution was $300 \mu\text{g}$ per millilitre.

Acetoacetanilide solution : Pure acetoacetanilide (B.D.H.) was further purified from ethanol. A 2% ethanolic solution of the reagent ($0.11 M$) was prepared.

Diverse ions . Aqueous solutions of other metals were prepared from their nitrates, chlorides or sulphates and a little quantity of an acid was added to prevent hydrolysis.

Apparatus : The absorbance measurements were carried out in a Hilger & Watts H700 Uvispek Spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cuvettes. A battery operated bench model Cambridge pH-meter was used for pH measurements.

Procedure : A definite quantity (150 to 900 μg) of the standard copper solution was taken in a 50 ml separatory funnel and 1.0 ml of the ethanolic solution of acetoacetanilide was added. The mixture was diluted to 25 ml. Exactly 10 ml of chloroform was then added and the pH of the aqueous layer was adjusted within 7.0 and 8.0 with aqueous ammonia (3*N*). The complex formed was taken into organic layer by vigorous shaking for a minute or two. The chloroform layer was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask, the traces of water were removed by adding a little anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance was measured at 340 $m\mu$.

R E S U L T S

Absorbance and validity of Beer's law : Absorbance curves were obtained with chloroform as the extracting solvent using different concentrations of copper keeping the experimental conditions same as above. The absorbance of chloroform solution was measured in the range 320 to 410 $m\mu$. Similarly, the reference solution was also prepared. Absorbance curves thereby obtained are shown in Fig.1, where absorbance below 320 $m\mu$ and above 400 $m\mu$ have been omitted. The absorbance of the reagent blank against chloroform has also been recorded.

Figure 1 shows that absorbance is maximum at about 330 $m\mu$ but the reagent has some absorption at this wave-length, while at 340 $m\mu$ the absorbance due to the reagent is negligible. In subsequent experiments, therefore, absorbance was measured at 340 $m\mu$ so that pure solvent could be used as reference.

When absorbance values due to varying concentrations of copper (II) were plotted, Beer's law was found to be obeyed for solutions containing 15 to 90 μg of the metal per millilitre of chloroform.

Selection of organic solvent : Possibilities of extraction with several organic solvents were studied. Chloroform was chosen as quantitative transfer was possible in a single extraction.

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Absorbance Curves of Copper (II)-acetoacetanilide complex in Chloroform.

Extraction and acidity of the solution : A set of copper solutions containing same amount of metal (450 μg) and 1 ml of the reagent solution were prepared and diluted to 25 ml. By adding ammonium hydroxide these solutions were adjusted to different pH values, with the aid of a pH meter. The complex was extracted with exactly 10 ml portion of chloroform from each of the solutions and the absorbance of each was measured at 340 $m\mu$. It was assumed that 100% extraction was possible between pH 7.1 and 8.0 as the aqueous layer did not show the presence of copper (II) when tested with ferrocyanide or cupron. The variation of extraction (%) against pH was obtained using molar absorptivity and is presented in Figure 2.

Effect of reagent concentration : In a set of experiments the amount of the reagent was varied from 5 to 30 mg per extraction maintaining all the other conditions same. It was observed that at least 20 mg of the reagent was required when an ethanolic solution of acetoacetanilide was used and the complex was formed before extraction. If the reagent was dissolved in chloroform, much larger amounts of the reagent were necessary.

Stability of colour : The absorbance of several copper-acetoacetanilide extracts containing different amounts of the metal were measured at an interval of 30 minutes, but no change was observed upto three hours.

FIG. 2

Fig. 2. Extraction (%) of Copper (II)-acetoacetanilide complex in Chloroform against pH.

Optimum concentration range, Sensitivity and Absorptivity : The optimum ranges for measurements corresponding to the wave-length 340 mμ, meeting the requirements laid down by Sandell¹⁴ was 6 to 45 μg/ml. of copper in chloroform. The sensitivity of the reaction¹⁴, i.e., the amount of copper corresponding to an absorbance of 0.001, has been calculated to be 0.063 μg per sq. cm. while the practical sensitivity corresponding to 0.01 absorbance is 0.6 μg of copper per sq. cm. Molar absorptivity value at 340 mμ was calculated to be 1004 ± 1.6%.

Effect of diverse ions : To determine the effects due to the presence of the metals commonly present in copper alloys, 100 μg of nickel (II), cobalt (II), manganese (II), zinc (II), lead (II), or aluminium (III) were mixed with a known amount of copper (II) solution and the extraction and absorbance measurements were carried on as described earlier. It was observed that there was no interference due to these foreign ions. The presence of mercury (II), magnesium (II), calcium (II) and barium (II) could also be tolerated at least upto 100 μg. There was no effect on the absorption value when 5 ml of an 1% solution of ammonium fluoride was added. However, tartrate, citrate or ethylene diamine

14. E. R. Sandell, *Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals*, Interscience, 1959, p. 83 and p. 97.

tetracetate prevented the colour formation. The estimation of copper was not possible when 20 μg or more of iron (III) was added, though the presence of it in smaller amounts could be masked by ammonium fluoride. The results of these experiments are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Determination of copper in presence of diverse ions

Cu ²⁺ taken : 45 μg /per ml of CHCl_3 pH 7.1 to 8.0				
Diverse Ion (100 μg)	Absorbance	Cu ²⁺ found (μg)	Relative Error (%)	
Ni ²⁺	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	
Co ²⁺	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	
Mn ²⁺	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	
Zn ²⁺	0.705, 0.71	44, 45	-2.2, nil	
Hg ²⁺	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	
Mg ²⁺	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	
Pb ²⁺	0.705, 0.71	44, 45	-2.2, -2.2	
Ca ²⁺	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	
Ba ²⁺	0.705, 0.71	44, 45	-2.2, nil	
Bi ³⁺	0.705, 0.705	44, 44	-2.2, -2.2	
Al ³⁺	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	
*F ⁻	0.71, 0.71	45, 45	nil, nil	

* as 5 ml of 1% aqueous NH_4F .

Determination of Copper in Brass or Bronze : About 0.1 g of brass was dissolved in 9M nitric acid digested on a hot water bath for one hour and evaporated to dryness. The mass was treated with water, the residue of metastannic acid, if any, was filtered and washed with dilute nitric acid. The filtrate and washing were collected and diluted to 100 ml, in a measuring flask, and a 5 ml portion of this solution was transferred into a separatory funnel and copper was extracted and determined following the method described in the heading "Procedure". Results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Determination of copper in alloys

Alloy	Composition (%)	Weight taken (g)	Copper found (%)	Relative Error (%)
Brass	Cu, 61.24	0.1060	61.25	+0.02
	Zn, 38.76	0.1112	61.28	+0.04
Bronze	Cu, 87.32		87.26	-0.06
	Sn, 8.46	0.1142		
	Pb, 1.98	0.1124	87.29	-0.03
	Zn, 1.20			
White metal	Cu, 4.20	0.1970	4.19	-0.23
	Sb, 9.30			
	Pb, 2.25	0.1909	4.17	-0.71
	Sn, rest			

Determination of Copper in White metal : About 0.2 g of the alloy was treated with 9M nitric acid, evaporated to dryness on a hot water bath and the mass was taken up with water. Metastannic acid was filtered off and washed with dilute nitric acid. The filtrate was collected in a 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark. A few milliliter portion of this solution was taken in a separatory funnel and copper was determined as described earlier. The results are presented in Table II.

Precision and Accuracy : When the measurements were carried out at 340 m μ the relative standard deviation was 1.03% in 30 determinations.

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